

not involve any lengthy procedure of solvent extraction. The new reagent is more suitable for comparatively higher concentration of mercury.

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Heats of Formation and Lattice Energies of Morpholine and Dioxan Complexes of Cobalt, Nickel, Copper and Zinc Fluoborates

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HEATS of formation and lattice energies of picoline complexes of copper fluoborate have been already reported¹. In this note heats of formation and lattice energies of morpholine and dioxan complexes of Co, Ni, Cu and Zn fluoborates have been determined. The isolation and characterisation of these complexes have been already reported²⁻³.

Fluoborate salts have been selected because the BF_4^- itself has got a tendency to take part in coordination and i.r. spectra study shows that BF_4^- serves as a bridge in the case of morpholine complex of cobalt².

In each case three readings were taken and the mean has been reported. Heats of formation (Q) determined by applying⁴ Hess's law of heat summation are given in the Table 1.

Calculation of Lattice Energy—Of the available equations⁵ for the calculation of lattice energy that of Kapustiniskii⁵ was found simple. But in these cases the values of ν (distance between the centre of the central cation and that of the co-ordinating atom) were not found in the literature and so the values of r_c (radii of the complex cations) and E_s (co-ordination energy) could not be calculated. Biltz and Grim⁶ have shown that the lattice energy of ammoniates is the sum of the two energies, namely the lattice energy of the ammonia free salts and the heat of formation of the ammoniates. In this present investigation, help has been taken from Biltz and Grim's work. Lattice energies of anhydrous fluoborates (U_1) were determined by two equations of Kapustiniskii⁵ and Yatsimirskii⁷. The values of lattice energies (U_2) are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Compound	U_1 , K cal/mole	Q K cal/mole	U_2 , K cal/mole
$\text{Co}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 2 Morpho	508.3	23.16	531.46
$\text{Co}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 1 Morpho	508.3	11.10	519.40
$\text{Cu}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 2 Morpho	504.66	32.90	537.46
$\text{Cu}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 1 Morpho	504.66	16.03	520.69
$\text{Zn}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 2 Morpho	493.0	22.72	515.72
$\text{Zn}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 1 Morpho	493.0	9.62	502.62
$\text{Co}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 2 Dioxan	508.3	34.83	543.13
$\text{Co}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 1 Dioxan	508.3	18.33	526.63
$\text{Ni}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 2 Dioxan	510.5	38.39	548.89
$\text{Ni}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 1 Dioxan	510.5	23.37	533.87
$\text{Cu}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 2 Dioxan	504.66	26.00	530.66
$\text{Cu}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 1 Dioxan	504.66	14.00	518.66
$\text{Zn}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 2 Dioxan	493.0	26.30	519.30
$\text{Zn}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ 1 Dioxan	493.0	12.52	505.52

It is found in all the cases that as the number of ligand molecules decreases in a particular metal complex, the lattice energy value also decreases. It seems that as the number of ligands increases the crystal becomes more densely packed and hence the lattice energy value increases.

Similarly the lattice energy value decreases when the number of ligand molecules decreases as the crystal now becomes less densely packed.

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TLC Separation of Some Inorganic Ions on Silica Gel-Ceric Molybdate Impregnated Layers

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RECENTLY Malik and coworkers¹, have reported the ion-exchange behaviour of ceric molybdate. In the present study, we have utilised the ion-exchange property of ceric molybdate for the TLC separation of some closely related inorganic ions.